

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF SOME TIPS AND STRATEGIES OF IELTS READING

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Ortiqova Durdona Nafiddin qizi

Pirmurodova Ruxsora Matyoqubovna

*1st year students at Djizzakh branch of The National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek*

Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi

*Supervisor: Assistant teacher in the department Foreign Languages at Djizzakh
branch of The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek*

Annotation: *This article gives information about several strategies and tips such as Primary skills needed, Searching and underlining key words Looking for synonyms and parallel expressions, Skimming (reading the text very quickly), Scanning (looking for something without reading) Reading for specific information which can be helpful for candidates for taking higher band score in READING section in ACADEMIC IELTS exam. In this article, candidates can learn the types of questions like matching headings, multiple-choice, true, false, not given and yes, no, not given questions. Also, we mentioned several ways of how to solve these type of questions easily and effectively.*

Key words: *matching heading, skimming, scanning, summary completion, yes, no, not given question, true, false, not given question and multiple-choice question.*

IELTS READING QUESTION TYPES.

MATCHING HEADINGS: you are asked to choose heading of paragraphs and match up them to the relevant paragraphs from a text. Matching heading question type is one of the most difficult question types in the IELTS exam for students. Why? The main reason is that the headings are usually very resembling to each other. Also, you have more headings than you need for the question.

MATCHING HEADING TIPS:

1. Do this type of question first it is on the test. By doing this you will have a chance to get the general meaning of the text as a whole. This will help you with the test of the questions that require you to take a more detailed look at the text
2. Check how many questions you need to answer.
3. Do not use any answer more than once.
4. Do not need to read the whole text.
5. Read the headings first and think about the topic of the text. Then, read the first, second and last sentences of the paragraph to understand the general meaning of the paragraph.
6. Identify and underline keywords within each heading.

7. Try to look for synonyms or other words that have a similar meaning to words or phrases in the headings so you can rule out the correct answers

8. **MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUESTIONS:** one question is given to you followed by four or five choices in which you have to choose the best one which will fit your answer.

MULTIPLE-CHOICE TIPS:

1. Read the instructions carefully, skim all the questions briefly to get an idea of the topics for which you will be searching when reading the text.

2. Try to predict the right answer before you read the text.

3. In multiple choice questions, remember to use the keywords in the question to help you find the right part of the text. Read that part again and consider all the options one by one.

4. Match the keywords in the question to their associated paragraph in the text. You need to know where to read to find the correct answer.

5. Locate the particular section of the paragraph in which the important information is located to find the answer.

6. You don't need to read the entire text from beginning to end because the questions follow the same order as the paragraphs.

7. The keyword you see in the question may not be written exactly the same as it is in the paragraph.

8. Only read the particular section of the paragraph which directly relates back to the question after you match the keyword or the synonym from the question to the corresponding paragraph.

SUMMARY COMPLETION: you will be given a summary of information from the text and there will be some gaps in that summary. You will either be given a list of words to fill the gaps with or asked to find the answers in the reading text. Your job is to insert some of the words from the list into the gaps; or if you are asked to fill the gaps with words from the text, there will be more words in the list that are required to fill the gaps. All of the information contained in the summary will also be contained in the reading text but they will use synonyms and paraphrasing. Therefore, don't expect to see the same words. The summary may relate to the whole passage or only a part of it and the text of the summary will follow the order of the text of the passage.

SUMMARY COMPLETION TIPS:

1. Read the instructions to the questions very carefully.

2. Skim through the summary. Ignoring the blanks to understand its general meaning.

3. Predict the right answers before looking at the options.

4. Don't waste time looking at parts of the passage that are not included in the summary.

5. You need to focus on keywords before and after the blank.

6. Check with the passage. You can use your keyword strategy to identify the correct part of the passage but remember you are looking for synonyms.

7. Check to see if your word is grammatical. Think about nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs.

8. The answers are mostly in order. Sometimes they'll all be in order; but once in a while, there will be an answer that comes before another answer. However, don't worry about this because the keywords are specific and easy to find.

COMPLETION TASKS: These tasks are note completion, flowchart completion, sentence completion, table completion, and summary completion tasks. **COMPLETION TASKS TIPS :** Here are some basic tips that you need to learn to deal with this type of question excellently:

1. There will be a words limit, so please read the instructions carefully and see the words limit that you need to write in order to fill in the gaps. There will be usually **NO MORE THAN ONE WORDS, TWO WORDS or THREE WORDS**, so underline this and remember while you fill in the exercise.

2. Secondly, usually for most tasks in IELTS reading, the questions in the tasks and the gaps are followed in the same order as they will appear in the text. However, please remember and keep in mind that when you see a completion task, the questions and the gaps will not necessarily follow the order that they will be shown in the text.

3. You should copy the words that you find in the text exactly the same way in order to fill in the gaps. Hence, they have to both fit grammatically and syntactically.

4. Try to predict what kind of words are missing, for example, a noun, a verb, an adjective or an adverb. The words before and after the gap help you understand what is missing.

5. You should underline key words that precede gaps. These keywords are going to guide you through the text in order to find where the correct answer is located. You should be careful of paraphrasing.

6. In IELTS, you should always concentrate on meanings, not on words. That is always helpful to be good at skimming and scanning techniques.

YES, NO, NOT GIVEN QUESTIONS: the YES, NO, NOT GIVEN questions are all about the writer's opinion. It's not about the facts but about what the writer thinks. If the answer is YES, it means that the statement in the question agrees with the claims of the writer. If the answer is NO, it means the statement is opposite; it contradicts the claims of the writer. NOT GIVEN means it is impossible to say what the writer thinks about.

YES, NO, NOT GIVEN TIPS:

1. Ignore anything you already know about the topic and don't make assumptions. Based your answers on the text only.

2. Identify any words that qualify the statement. For example, some, all, mainly, often, always and occasionally. These words are there to test if you have read the whole statement because they can change the meaning. Be careful.

3. When you see verbs that qualify statements such as know, suggest, claim, and believe. For example, “the woman claimed she was a doctor” and “the women is a doctor” mean they are different.

4. Don't skim and scan the text. To find the correct answer, you will have to read the appropriate part of the text very carefully in order to understand what the writer means.

5. Don't look for words that exactly match those in the statements. Instead, you should look for synonyms.

6. If you can't find the information you are looking for, then it is probably NOT GIVEN. Don't waste time looking for something that is not there.

7. Answers are in the same order they appear in the text. Do not waste time going back.

TRUE, FALSE, NOT GIVEN QUESTIONS: you will be given a number of factual statements and you have to check in the text if they are true, false or not given. The TRUE, FALSE, NOT GIVEN questions are all about factual information in the passage. It's not about opinions; it's about fact. TRUE means that the statement in the question agrees with the information in the passage. FALSE means the statement in the question contradicts the information in the Passage (“contradicts” means it's the opposite meaning). NOT GIVEN means there is no information on this. This task is used to assess the candidate's ability to find the particular information found in the passage.

TRUE, FALSE, NOT GIVEN TIPS:

1. Read the instructions carefully and make sure you know if it is a true/ false/ not given questions

2. Read all the statements carefully. Trying to understand what the whole sentence means rather than simply highlighting keywords.

3. You need to find the right part of the text before you can answer the question. Remember that the questions follow the text.

4. Finding key ideas in the text.

5. Look for expressions of uncertainty. Look for modal verbs like could, might, or must. Look for expressions which indicate uncertainty, such as suggest, think, claim, believe, and know. For example, it is thought that or many scientists believe that.

6. If you can't find the answer or if you are really unsure, mark it as NOT GIVEN and move on to the next question.

7. If the question in the reading test is TRUE, FALSE, NOT GIVEN, you must remember to write TRUE or FALSE or NOT GIVEN on your answer sheet; you can't write YES or NO. That means if the answer is TRUE and you write YES, the answer will be marked wrong.

8. You can write a letter instead of a word for your answer. That means if your answer is TRUE, you can write only T. It still means true and IELTS will give you a correct answer for that one point.

In summary, the main key is to identify the types of questions provided in the text, while doing the passages the candidates ought to clarify them how to deal with the questions. The reason why to it first is each type of the questions has own strategy to find the answer. Moreover, the takers should have not only wide range of vocabulary or techniques but also experience to follow the time management.

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